

Improvements to Implementation Methodology for CC-IoT

Atta Ur Rehman Shah
Department of Computer Science,
Lahore University of Management
Science, Pakistan
19030048@lums.edu.pk

Aoun Aftab
Department of Computer Science,
Comsats University Islamabad,
Sahiwal Campus, Pakistan
aounaftab@cuisahiwal.edu.pk

Muhammad Shujaat
Department of Computer Science,
Bahria University Lahore
Campus, Pakistan
mshujaat.bulc@bahria.edu.pk

Abstract—Modern “Internet of Things” (IoT) networks have become increasingly sophisticated, capable of extreme autonomous computing, and boast device counts in the millions (if not billions). In addition to the prevalence of consumer IoT devices (such as smartphones and televisions), sensory IoT devices are commonly seen in industry, agriculture, city planning etc. As the IoT global network continues to expand, there are crucial data volume, velocity and security requirements that must be addressed. This report will examine the use of Cloud Computing (CC) in handling these considerations and how it has become ubiquitous with IoT. It will consider the many benefits provided to IoT networks through integration with CC. However, there are still shortfalls experienced even with these measures in place. Thus this report shall also analyze recent research work that seeks to improve upon the traditional IoT implementations in the aforementioned areas of interest.

Keywords- IOT; Cloud Computing; Information Security; Networks

1. INTRODUCTION & BACKGROUND

Kevin Ashton is credited as the first person to make use of the phrase “Internet of things” (IoT) as far back as 1999 [1]. Since then it has become a term used to describe a framework of connected computer devices, each their own unique identifier (UID). Naturally, the IoT most people are familiar with is the World Wide Web, which is a global network of an estimated 31 billion connected devices in 2020 [2].

Even at a smaller scale though (say, district level), an IoT network can be extremely intricate and handle thousands of devices which accumulatively produce significant quantities of data. Indeed, the emergence of “Big Data” as a field of study in recent years indicates how traditional data processing architecture is lacking [3]. This brings us to **Cloud Computing (CC)**, which has become a popular solution to meet the ever-rising storage and computational requirements of IoT networks. For instance, consider the motivating scenario below:

The city of Amsterdam launched a “smart city” project in 2009, whose goal was to modernize various aspects of the urban center’s infrastructure [4]. Wireless and wired IoT devices have been placed throughout the city (including cameras, weather sensors etc.) to provide useful data that can then be used by the city’s administration to make informed decisions of governance.

Many software applications have been developed through this initiative that citizens can download to their

smartphones to gain benefits. As an example, one of the apps allows urbanites who own parking spaces to rent them out to visitors in the crowded downtown area. The city also benefits, as by inducting more users into their network they are able to build a more holistic picture of citizen data — parking demand by sector in this case.

The above scenario is only a small slice of the potential within IoT networks, especially now as users often own multiple IoT devices and carry them where ever they go. **Table 1** shows some other applications where IoT can be found as well as example use cases:

Application	Example Use Case(s)
Predictive Maintenance [5]	> Fault detection in industrial fabrication processes. > Optimal lifespan calculation for tools and machine parts.
Smart metering [6]	> Automatic billing for citizen utilities consumption.
Asset Tracking [7]	> Automatic air-traffic control systems. > Delivery status tracking in courier services.
Vehicular Connectivity [8]	> Automatic speeding ticket generation. > Automatic emergency response systems (e.g. Onstar).
Fleet Management [9]	> Remote vehicle disabling based on geo-fencing.

Table 1: Examples of Real-World IoT Applications

So, it becomes clear that IoT is already an integral part of many individuals’ lives and has tremendously affected the industrial sector, agriculture, businesses and much more. We have already taken note of the sheer scale that these networks operate on, due to the number of devices and volume of data transferred. In the next section we shall take a closer look to identify what specific issues currently demand attention when constructing IoT networks.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Extensive research has been conducted in the area of IoT focused Service Oriented Computing (SOC), particularly as it pertains to CC [10]. The papers we intend to cover in this report have identified a number of key problems and challenges and in the interest of focusing our discussion's scope, we have formulated characteristics based on their solutions presented in these papers. This report shall concern itself with how IoT services are "exposed" within their networks (i.e. how they are made discoverable for end users or other devices), and the implications different techniques will have on performance. Additionally, specific attention shall be given to Event-driven and Context-driven IoT systems, as these often have some of the most strenuous and demanding requirements when it comes to response time.

Another growing concern among the public has been that of security. More and more sensitive data is being kept on IoT networks, such as personal user correspondence, crypto-currency, sensory data (in the case of administrative organizations) and so forth. The danger here is that malicious parties may attempt to illicitly gain access to data within an IoT network, or perhaps even tamper with data that is being transferred to and from IoT devices and the cloud. Average users have also become more aware of the importance of online privacy in recent times, and thus the providers of IoT services often have to keep their security standards high to maintain faith. In certain cases it may even be that the trustworthiness of the providers is called into question and thus end users may avoid IoT services that they feel unfairly exploit user data for their own benefit. So, it behooves IoT service providers to keep security a top priority. As an example, some popular mobile text-messaging services like Whatsapp offer End-to-End Encryption (E2EE) to protect the communication of users [11]. In theory, it means that even the publishers of these applications are unable to decrypt private messages sent using their service.

3. AIMS & OBJECTIVES

This report aims to fulfill the following general aims. This list also provides an overview of the structure that the remainder of this report will follow:

1. *Provide clearly specified definitions for key terms that pertain to CC-based IoT networks in a service oriented environment.*
2. *Review the literature in this area to identify the weaknesses of traditional CC/IoT methodologies and examine the implementations used when processing and storing data in an event-driven and/or real-time environment.*
3. *Identify the weaknesses of traditional CC-IoT methodologies when protecting against malicious parties.*
4. *Review how the literature in this field has attempted to investigate these issues and provide a comparative analysis of the solutions that have been proposed.*
5. *Identify possible weaknesses with solutions proposed in the existing literature.*
6. *Provide some further insight into the expected direction that may be taken by further work in these areas and in what ways such research will need to improve to build off of the current literature.*

Based on the above aims the following general research questions have been derived. This report will primarily be concerned with answering these questions:

1. *What techniques and methodologies can be used to improve the current models in place to provide superior provisioning of Data-Centric IoT Services in the cloud?*
2. *What specifically is lacking within the current models?*
3. *How can the current models be made more efficient and context-driven?*

As this report proceeds, these questions will be further expanded upon to more detailed levels of granularity. Thus, in our literature review we shall analyze the various papers discussed in this report under the following subsections:

1. *Structural Implementation of CC based IoT Networks*
2. *Context-driven/Real-time Techniques in IoT Networks*
3. *Security Concerns in CC based IoT Networks*

Each of these subsections will then be further divided on an issue by issue basis, with references to the relevant papers.

4. KEY DEFINITIONS

Before continuing, it will be worthwhile to specify some technical parameters within which this discussion will take place. These are important preliminary definitions that are useful to know for the purposes of understanding the literature review section:

1. **Physical Context:** IoT device dependencies that are based on external factors (e.g. geographic location of the device, the time of day, potential outlier events such as emergencies, holidays, accidents etc.). Situates a device within the real world.
2. **Temporal Context:** A specific physical context which can be further into real-time, time-range or date-range.
3. **Publish/Subscribe Model:** A methodology for IoT implementation which involves the use of middleware. IoT devices that make their data available are publishers and will not have any knowledge of the Subscribers who receive the data. Thus only the raw content and dataset types are transferred.
4. **5 "V's" of Big Data:** A common phraseology used that refers to 5 dimensional characteristics in which Big Data is commonly evaluated:
 - a. **Volume:** The quantity of generated and stored data.
 - b. **Variety:** The range of data types and nature of the data.
 - c. **Velocity:** The rate at which new data is produced and added to the dataset. Often in real-time.
 - d. **Veracity:** The accuracy of the data within its use case context. Dependent on physical context and sensor quality.
 - e. **Value:** A derived metric that is dependent on the other "Vs". Also refers to the potential utility that can be extracted from the dataset.
5. **IoT Resource Registry:** An organized set of Unique Resource Identifiers (URIs) for all devices/services within the IoT network. Used as a sort of address book to locate and/or refer to specific IoT entities/nodes.
6. **Context Driven and Real Time IoT (CARIoT):** As the same suggests, an IoT framework that is useful for real-time provisioning of services in an efficient manner by being based on contextual features in the dataset.

7. **Cloud Manufacturing (CMfg):** An industry paradigm that leverages the IoT for the purposes of aiding in the complete life cycle of a manufacturing process, including designing, producing, testing, and maintenance of a product.
8. **Virtualization:** In the context of CC, virtualization refers to the partitioning of cloud resources to users on the basis of software divisions of processing power for the same shared hardware/servers.

5. LITERATURE REVIEW

For ease of understanding, this section has been subdivided into multiple sections on an issue-by-issue basis.

5.1 Structural Implementation

5.1.1 Deployment and Manufacturing Concerns

Traditionally, IoT registries are fairly simplistic, often representing the data in a tabular form. The registry is often centralized and only accessible from one place in these types of networks, and the distinction between IoT devices is primitive, usually only grouping resources/nodes as either “Applications” or “Devices”.

[12] discusses challenges that have been addressed for CC based IoT in certain manufacturing contexts. Though initially CMfg might seem like a niche use-case that does not apply to most of IoT networks, in reality the principles that are relevant here can be integrated into all large-scale/long-term IoT systems for efficiency gains. Note that the term “manufacturing” is not being used as it is in layman’s terms (the fabrication of a physical product). As this paper describes: when applied, it will manifest itself in areas such as the design and manufacture of all services that can be provided over the IoT. Additionally, it will also be relevant in the case of deploying services and upgrading the current network e.g., replacing older legacy sensors with lossless optical fiber sensors for accurate and real-time monitoring. This paper notes that the majority of work in the IoT emphasizes the process of data gathering and recording it but studies on how to optimize techniques from the deployment side are not as fully fleshed-out.

[12] proposes an evolution of the traditional CC system by iterating on the original publish/subscribe model, where there are three kinds of users defined in a CMfg system:

1. **Providers:** who own and make available the services and resources. These could be a single user, an organization or some other third party.
2. **Operators:** who operate and administer the CMfg platform to ensure the delivery of services and resources to all other users in the network
3. **Consumers:** who are the “subscribers” in this model, and they request and lease the use of the services in the network from operators on a need-by basis with the cost proportional to their usage. Fittingly, this is similar to the pay-as-you-go system that many CC providers have adopted as it provides maximum flexibility to the end user.

The amorphous nature of CMfg systems and the relationship between these user types have been described in this paper as well. Based on the above, three phases have been outlined at a high level:

Phase 1: Perception→Online/Wired Connectivity → Acquisition:

In this phase, various idle or newly created services and resources from providers are intelligently evaluated by operators

and connected into the wider network. Then, they are automatically managed and controlled using existing IoT devices based on predetermined functions, similar to an event driven architecture (see **section 5.2.1** below). On top of this, detailed metadata must also be provided or generated for these services and resources so their exact nature can be exactly evaluated, which will prove crucial for the next phase.

Phase 2: Aggregation → Management → Optimal Allocation:

Because the metadata of these services/resources is provided they can be “virtualized” and then encapsulated into different service classes based on specialized algorithms.

Phase 3: On-demand Usage:

Different users in the IoT network now have a selection from the organized and virtual services and can assemble them in a customized virtual environment according to their needs.

To accomplish this, the structure of the network has been specified in [12]:

- **IoT Layer:** deals with service discoverability, connectivity, and request processing.
- **Service Layer:** manages service classification/grouping, and optimal allocation of resources in the cloud. It can be further divided into the
 - Resource Virtualization Layer
 - Cloud Service Layer
 - Application System Layer
- **Application Layer:** Responsible for maximizing the availability of services for end users throughout the manufacturing cycle.
- **Support Layer:** Provides interfacing for the other three sub-layers by providing a knowledge base that can be accessed for metadata and an internet sub-layer for wider discoverability and connectivity.

A more detailed look at the architectural design can be seen in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: Architecture of CC based IoT in light of CMfg

However, ultimately this structural implementation is simply a more detailed version of what we began our discussion with i.e. a tabular model. Although there is greater nuance in the categorization of nodes, in the end the main performance bottleneck comes for the middleware and from the repeated accessing of

metadata for resource discovery. When combined with the protocols and APIs used in these networks to codify messages, the overhead only rises. We will need to look elsewhere to try and resolve some of these issues

5.1.2 IoT Resource Registration

As mentioned, reasonable expectations would dictate that there will be a daunting number of IoT services in the network, and so an efficient storage mechanism for tracking IoT resources is needed. This will be primarily dependent on the model used for the IoT resource registry. Although CMfg oriented strategy when building the architecture of the IoT does provide some benefit, it does not scale as well as we require. The basic/traditional mode has had a strict structure, usually a cloud-based Structured Query Language (SQL) database. However, the performance of such a registry is poor when scaled for such a large network, as pointed out in [13]. This paper also notes that resources in IoT systems often relate to each other semantically (based on physical and temporal contexts). A tabular model is not an accurate projection of these aspects within the network. In such models the metadata accompanying each resource is the only meaningful data that can be used to discover services, which is not very helpful in service selection problems because of the overhead incurred both in having to store this metadata for each resource somewhere but also due to access times.

An alternative provided in [13] is a hierarchical modelling and abstraction framework. This is known as the **Service Access Tree (SAT)** and serves a superior way to organize services within the IoT. This is a graphical representation of the registry, where IoT services are defined in a tree-like structure. There are two types of nodes, context nodes and resource nodes. Resource nodes are leaf nodes in the tree and each is representative of a singular IoT service/device based on its URI. Context nodes represent groupings of resource nodes and of other context nodes that are its children. Thus, physical or temporal dimensions can potentially be incorporated into the IoT registry via this model. It should also be noted that a context node has access to the data and the context of all of its children.

Figure 2: Example of SAT for a city

Consider **Figure 2**, which contains an example Context Action Tree (CAT) and its associated SAT (The CAT is simply the abstracted SAT with generic labels). Here we see the structural breakdown of a city has been used as the context for the SAT, where the root node represents the city. Children of the root at each height level demarcate smaller and smaller divisions of the city based on topology (districts, streets etc.) until we reach resource nodes which could pertain to all sorts of devices (cameras, weather sensors etc.). As mentioned in [13] this provides two main benefits.

Firstly, it improves service access times as now context is employed to help give a topological classification to nodes, and

it is much faster to traverse the tree than a tabular dataset. The specific resource node is travelled to on the basis of contextual information. Secondly, if data from a cluster of IoT services is needed then SAT will be more efficient than a tabular implementation, as one simply needs to access the parent node of the resource nodes whose data is required (e.g., if data was to be collected for all resource nodes on a certain street). This helps mitigate the need for vast quantities of repetitive metadata.

5.2 Context-driven/Real-time Techniques

5.2.1 Event Processing

[13] makes extensive use of the smart city analogy (similar to our motivating scenario from the introduction), going so far to provide real world examples of its implementation that were used for empirical testing within the paper. As it explains, these IoT networks (like many others) rely on two major components: the physical portion (the IoT devices/resources) and the cloud portion. Of course, the cloud portion also exists on some physical hardware, but for our purposes this abstraction will suffice.

We see in [13] that the IoT model used needs to be event-driven. It is on the cloud where operations are usually carried out on extracted data. As events occur throughout the city, they will provide heterogeneous data that can trigger a multitude of differing responses within the cloud. This in turn results in different return data to the respective parties.

For instance, a festival held in the city center on a certain day will result in an uptick of traffic in the area. This information can trigger an alert notification to citizens who have their smartphones connected to the IoT so that they can plan their day accordingly. This paper suggests a solution that involves empowering context nodes with the capacity to create event objects (i.e. notifications). These events allow them to add or remove children and also sever/establish connections with a resource node. This creates much needed robustness within the system. In our smart city example, this could manifest itself in citizens who move throughout the urban area with their IoT devices. As their devices are not stationary, it is important that these functions exist to be able to accurately model the movement of individuals throughout the city.

This notion of incorporating events into the IoT service framework is also explored in [14]. In traditional computing architecture, real time response is often achieved using parallel process service execution, but this proves to be inadequate on its own once scaled up to large IoT network sizes. Thus, in this paper, a need for an event driven model is once again advocated for (as it was in [13]), where events detected by IoT devices lead to triggered protocols for real-time level response. However, here we see an architecture oriented approach, dubbed **Event Driven architecture (EDA)**. In this case, events are propagated from the data recorded on components to one or more services. When an event is activated it is able to affect multiple service level interactions. This is different from both the normative approach and what is presented in [13] where there is just one sender and one receiver per communication channel. In EDA the mode of communication is many-to-many. Not only does this add an element of multi-parallelism to EDA, but it creates an asynchronous functional environment. Asynchronous communication has been shown to provide significant performance improvements in response times as services are able “share” events via an Event Bus (EB).

5.2.2 Historical Data Provisioning

Although the trend has shifted to sophisticated microcomputers on the consumer product side, many IoT devices

are still rudimentary in processing power and function as little more than sensors. Additionally, IoT devices with portability are said to be “**transient**”, which refers to their limited battery lives and tendency to move throughout the IoT subspaces. Along the edges of the IoT, devices frequently will lose connection and rejoin the network at irregular intervals. Consequently, exposed services are never 100% reliable, (as those who have attempted to use GPS in tunnels can attest to). However, just because the resource nodes are not connected to the system does not mean that a user’s data requirements are on standby.

Historical Data Provisioning can help plug the gap in these cases by providing a fallback option. Although not always feasible, in many situations even a simple calculated mean of the previously recorded data can suffice. An example is illustrated in [13], where an end user can be provided with weather predictions based on the climate recording for previous dates at that time of the year. Analyzing historical data is also often valued for the purposes of pattern recognition and prediction making. For instance, by analyzing electricity consumption of a sector from the past data, a municipality can make reasonable forecasts for what the projected demand will be next year. As this paper explains, it will involve augmenting the previously mentioned SAT. In a service provisioning IoT network, each node of the SAT can be used to maintain a list of data items gathered by its children. In the case of resource nodes such as sensors, this would translate into something like environmental data. Naturally, historical data in context nodes would be some aggregation of the data from resource nodes under it.

Additionally, when data analysis occurs the temporal context plays an important role as it often determines the bounds of the data being taken into consideration. A time range or date range filter can either be used as a search parameter for data or used to chart trends in the data. In [13] The CARIoT is designed to process these requests within context nodes. These context nodes have access to the historical data (pooled from resource nodes) and so the data aggregation is recursive as it traverses the sub-trees of the chosen context node until the relevant data has been extracted from all resource nodes that satisfy the requester’s filters. It is important to realize that the SAT is only a software level abstraction of the real-world IoT devices, but it uses decidedly physical dimensions as the basis for this abstraction. Furthermore, the historical data is usually stored on the cloud rather than on the (relatively) computationally Spartan IoT devices themselves.

Figure 3 shows a high level overview of the structure of such an implementation of the cloud within the CARIoT framework.

Figure 3: Overview of the CARIoT Structure

5.3 Security Implementation & Consideration

5.3.1 Event Based Access Control

[15] attempts to utilize an event driven approach to security. Here the focus is on access control in particular. Consider the following motivating scenario:

A factory is part of an IoT network and has a pH-level monitoring system for chemical vats full of product. The system consists of a sensor that is attached to a fine probe suspended within the vat. Based on the data received from this system, chemicals are released accordingly into the vat to maintain ideal conditions. The probe/sensor is the IoT device and can transmit readings rapidly for an unlimited amount of time. So, the sensor is considered to be an “untrusted” entity as it is possible either due to component failure or interference from a malicious party that incorrect readings begin to stream from the device. Impersonating the sensor can also allow network hijackers to make use of other common exploits such as buffer overflow and SQL injection.

In this paper, the system proposed to combat such a situation is the **Event-based Access Control (EbAC) Framework**. This framework is intended for the processing module of IoT systems, where policy settings have been predetermined and are used to manage the control flow and the data flow. Resources are finite and in many cases the velocity demand of the network will mean that it is important the computation process is not starved of data. The EbAC access control comprises a controller module and a policy module. As shown in **Figure 4**, a triggered event by either the kernel or by a process will lead to capability checking that is handled by the EbAC. Based on these if the system feels like privileges should be restricted it will act accordingly.

While this approach is technically “event-driven”, it is not context-driven. As a result it is plagued by a number of shortcomings. For instance, it only accounts for the most rudimentary of malicious exploits and attack vectors that could be employed against the IoT system. Additionally, in a direct EbAC the overhead incurred for adding extra layers of encryption may make the system too inefficient for its intended purposes.

However, we shall see in the next subsection a different security implementation that does, in fact, take context into account and examines how this provides certain improvements over a purely event-driven approach.

5.3.2 Correlation Set Based Risk Assessment

The network aspect of the IoT is often the most vulnerable portion, as it contains the stream of data as well as providing the most opportunities for malicious parties to gain illicit access. IoT devices themselves are usually low power, transient and not usually directly connected to other resource nodes within the CC based IoT. Even if a malicious party is able to hack such a device they do not generally compromise the integrity of the system as badly as they would have had they infiltrated the cloud itself. However, gaining access is only one of the security concerns that presents itself. Disruption can be an equally viable tactic for some malicious parties and it may be enough to simply make end-users’ “think” their devices are compromised. Thus, even without the cloud itself being attacked, users may lose faith in the security provisions in the IoT network and the reputation/business of services will suffer. With the high tally of IoT devices out there, there needs to be an efficient mechanism to assess security concerns for an architecture.

Figure 4 - The IoT Ecosystem with SIEM

Doing this can prove a major challenge though. There are large disparities and heterogeneities within the network layer. Not only will different nodes have different stakes for communication, but the standards and protocols differ wildly. While some APIs (such as those built on SOAP) have inbuilt encryption measures to protect message integrity, not all of the commonly used protocols share this trait. In the development of security solutions, [16] brings an important perspective that is already familiar to us: an event-driven automated management approach. **Security Information Event Management (SIEM)** makes use of correlation sets to identify threats and will then respond to minimize the damaging impact when these threats are detected. **Figure 4** (previous page) shows the integration pattern of Security Information Management (SIM) and Security Event Management (SEM) to form SIEM and also how it fits within the IoT structure.

Table 2 shows a small sample of a vulnerability correlation set. Potential attack vectors that the SIEM uses to assess risk are represented in this set. Note the multiple dimensions of evaluation, which is based on contextual factors. Thus each potential vulnerability type is categorized based on its attributes to calculate an overall threat level. From this the network can act accordingly (e.g., instate a shutdown of afflicted devices to prevent further spread of malware, send an alert to the relevant user to make them aware of the situation etc.)

This particular implementation of SIEM has 18 values for **X** which cover descriptors of vulnerabilities and the potential attack vector(s). Thus, it is able to handle a much wider variety of security threat events than EbAC. On top of this, this system does not rely only on authentication to deal with malicious attacks. Instead, it is able to evaluate the specific attributes of a security threat. Even in the case of a successful attack, the system will be in a position it will be in a position to detect and shut down the affected node(s) to minimize spread and reduce losses.

Use of a Weak Password		✓		...	
Storage Location For Updates Files is Writable				...	
...

Table 2 - Sample of SIEM Correlation Set

6. DISCUSSION & ANALYSIS

All of the various papers discussed in the literature review deal with interrelated aspects of the CC based IoT framework for the purposes of improving efficiency and security. By examining the results we can draw the following conclusions to answer the questions posed in the Aims and Objectives section.

6.1 The Power of Event-Driven and Context - Driven Architecture Combined

We observe that the most effective solutions and implementations from the aforementioned research papers have generally incorporated both of these concepts into their framework. This is applicable not only in the cases of response time but also when it came to the question of security.

Improvements can be made from a number of potential vectors. An IoT service registry that makes use of a hierarchical SAT is extremely beneficial for a number of reasons. Firstly, it contextualizes the organization of IoT resources and services based on physical factors, which proves useful later when attempting to incorporate CARIoT as the groundwork has been laid already. It improves access time for services as filters based on these physical factors makes it easy to traverse a relatively small part of the tree to reach the desired resource or context node. However, this method still suffers from a weakness in that it is dependent on synchronous communication between nodes. We also saw how asynchronous communication can be achieved by adopting an Event Bus that is accessible for the nodes within the IoT network. Through this EDA, wait times are reduced as this allows one trigger to affect multiple services and resource nodes without having to wait for a return message. Though the concepts of EDA and CARIoT came from separate papers, a combination of both approaches should provide the best of both worlds and maximally optimize results.

6.2 Rethinking Deployment & Management.

Although EDA and CARIoT are beneficial and provide massive gains over a purely CMfg system, they neglect a critical aspect of the IoT implementation: deployment. This is a consideration that can easily be overlooked. Part of the reason for this is that many highly adopted IoT systems have already been constructed and deeply ingrained into the world (like the World Wide Web) and the labor/capital costs to completely restructure them from the ground up would be infeasible. However, this does not mean that the philosophy of the CMfg approach cannot find use.

“Smart Cities” are becoming increasingly popular government ventures and fresh, medium scale IoT systems continue to be implemented throughout industry. Additionally, multiple niches of the internet have adopted a CMfg approach for their specialized services (e.g. Server hosting providers like AWS). Thus, it is worthwhile to consider the lessons learned from CMfg

Vulnerability	X ₀ (Request Exception?)	X ₁ (Authentication Exception?)	X ₂ (Input Exception?)	...	X ₁₈ (Physical Interface?)
Lack of Control Against DoS Attacks	✓	✓	✓	...	✓

to design a more cohesive experience where the roles of users, providers and operators are clearly defined and virtualization has been strongly integrated into the cloud to present more flexibility for both end-users and a more optimized use of hardware in the cloud. This in conjunction with the innovations of Event-based and context driven CC-IoT networks is a composite solution that provides the optimal benefits of all the different techniques on display.

6.3 Improving System Robustness using Historical Data Provision & Risk Management

Although these two concepts deal with different aspects of the IoT, they are in fact closely related and can be used in tandem with each other for reinforcement and support. For instance, the ability to refer to historical data will allow a system that needed to partially shut down due to a malicious attack to continue to operate in some capacity. Thus, the sort of events where historical data provision is useful does not only apply to random events (such as transient IoT devices/services becoming unavailable). Furthermore, the historical data also provides another dimension of risk analysis and assessment, as anomalous values are easier to detect. This could potentially add even more dimensions to the correlation set and further increase the robustness of the IoT network.

7. CONCLUSION

There are a number of concerns that need to be addressed when it comes to the subject of CC based IoT implementation. In this paper we have taken a look at some of these issues, including structural implementations and how these can affect factors such as response time, propensity for service discovery and data security. Through the use of examples such as the “smart city scenario”, an allegory was drawn that comprehensively demonstrated the benefits of Event and Context Driven approaches when constructing CC based IoT networks. All of the approaches surveyed and discussed have their own merits, and in many ways they can work in tandem with each other. An ideal approach would leverage the advantages of all the methodologies and technologies discussed to optimize the IoT network and create the most robust framework that is highly resistant to malicious attacks.

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